

Numerical Analysis of Flow characteristics of a NACA0017 Airfoil

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ABSTRACT

The design and optimization of airfoils, which are essential components in various engineering applications like wind energy systems, turbine blades, and airplane wings, rely significantly on aerodynamic analysis. The aerodynamic performance of the symmetric airfoil NACA0017, focusing on its drag and lift coefficients under varying conditions have been analyzed in this paper. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations using ANSYS Fluent version 22R1 were employed to model the airflow over the airfoil at a 0° angle of attack, for different $Re \in (1 \times 10^5, 6 \times 10^5)$. The results are analyzed and presented through key aerodynamic parameters, including the drag coefficient, lift coefficient, velocity contours, and pressure coefficient across various Reynolds numbers. These findings provide valuable insights into the influence of flow characteristics on airfoil performance, highlighting variations in aerodynamic forces and pressure distribution. Results predicted minimal lift generation, as expected for a symmetric airfoil at this orientation, while the drag coefficient was well-characterized under steady-state conditions. These findings provide a foundation for understanding aerodynamic behavior of NACA0017 airfoil in low-drag applications.

KEYWORDS: NACA0017 airfoil; computational fluid dynamics (CFD); drag and lift coefficients; pressure coefficient

1 INTRODUCTION

Aerodynamic analysis plays a critical role in the design and optimization of airfoils, which are essential components in various engineering applications, including wind energy systems, turbine blades, and aircraft wings. Among the numerous airfoil profiles, the symmetric NACA 0017 stands out for its simplicity and versatility (Das Karmakar and Chattopadhyay 2022). Unlike cambered airfoils, which generate lift due to their asymmetrical shape, symmetric airfoils have identical upper and lower surfaces, resulting in zero lift at a 0° angle of attack. This characteristic makes them ideal for applications requiring balanced aerodynamic forces, such as vertical stabilizers and helicopter rotor blades.

The NACA0017 airfoil is a symmetric airfoil design developed by the National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics (NACA). Its nomenclature follows the standard four-digit system used by NACA. First Digit (0) indicates the maximum camber as a percentage of the chord length. A '0' signifies no camber, meaning the airfoil is symmetric. Second Digit (0) denotes the position of the maximum camber from the leading edge in tenths of the chord length. A '0' indicates that the maximum camber is at the leading edge. Third and Fourth Digits (17) represent the maximum thickness of the airfoil as a percentage of the chord length. Here, '17' means the maximum thickness is 17% of the chord. Therefore, NACA0017 refers to a symmetric airfoil with no camber and a maximum thickness of 17% of the chord length. This airfoil design is commonly used in applications where symmetrical lift characteristics are desired, such as in certain aircraft control surfaces and rotor blades.

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has become a reliable tool for analyzing airfoil aerodynamics, providing detailed insights into flow separation, turbulence, and boundary layer behavior (Kumar and Ghosh 2025; Lefebvre et al. 2018). The Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations, commonly employed in aerodynamic simulations, have been extensively validated against experimental data for various airfoil geometries (Merryisha, Rajendran, and Khan 2022; Zhang et al. 2021; Zheng and Chen 2024). Previous studies on symmetric airfoils have demonstrated the effectiveness of RANS-

based turbulence models in predicting aerodynamic performance across different flow conditions (Tongsawang 2015; Wang and Agarwal 2021).

Koca et al. (Koca et al. 2022) conducted an experimental investigation into vortex formation over the NACA-4412 WT airfoil, analyzing the influence of Reynolds number and angle of attack (AoA) on the development of recirculating vorticity. Their study provided valuable insights into the aerodynamic behavior of the airfoil under varying flow conditions. An experimental study on the formation of a laminar separation bubble (LSB) on the surface of the NACA 663-018 airfoil was conducted by O'Meara and Mueller (O'meara and Mueller 1987). Their findings revealed that an increase in Reynolds number led to a reduction in the size of the LSB, highlighting the influence of flow conditions on boundary layer behavior.

Khoury et al. [28] conducted a 3D performance analysis of three different airfoil profiles: NACA 0018, NACA 0021, and NACA 634-221 used in VAWT. Similarly, Hashem and Mohamed (Hashem and Mohamed 2018) explored the performance of 24 distinct airfoil shapes utilized in three-bladed H-rotor Darrieus VAWT by testing a rotor incorporating. Additionally, Mohamed (Mohamed 2012) investigated the aerodynamic performance using 20 different symmetrical and asymmetrical blade configurations for Darrieus turbine, including five FX-series, four A-series, four S-series, and seven NACA-series airfoils.

Previous studies on airfoil performance improvement have primarily focused on fixed Re conditions. However, the effects of varying inlet velocities on the flow over the NACA 0017 airfoil have not been thoroughly investigated or reported in existing research. A review of the literature revealed no studies addressing this aspect. This report examines the aerodynamic performance of the NACA 0017 airfoil at a 0° angle of attack, focusing on drag and lift coefficients under subsonic flow conditions. The study is conducted under Normal Temperature and Pressure (NTP) conditions, ensuring well-defined air properties such as density, specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity, and viscosity. Aluminum is selected as the airfoil material due to its advantageous mechanical and thermal properties, making it a widely used choice in engineering applications (Sharma and Grewal 2023). In section 2, a detailed description of the computational domain, initial and boundary conditions, and validation studies have been provided. Section 3 presents the results along with an in-depth analysis and discussion. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the key conclusions drawn from the study.

2. COMPUTATIONAL MODELING

2.1 Computational domain

The aerodynamic performance of the NACA 0017 airfoil is evaluated through numerical analysis using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations in ANSYS Fluent version 22R1. To simplify the study, three-dimensional effects are disregarded, and a two-dimensional approach is adopted. The computational domain is defined with an inlet positioned 7.5 times the chord length (C) upstream and an outlet located 15C downstream (Rezaeiha, Kalkman, and Blocken 2017), where the chord length is set to 1 meter. Figure 1 illustrates the computational setup.

Figure 1: Computational domain

2.2 Governing Equations

For the aerodynamic analysis of the NACA 0021 airfoil using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), the following fundamental equations are essential:

$$C_D = \frac{D}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 A} \quad C_L = \frac{L}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 A}$$

Where C_D is drag coefficient, C_L is lift coefficient, L is the lift force, D is the drag force, A is the reference area and V is the freestream velocity.

$$Re_x = \frac{\rho U_\infty L}{\mu}$$

This Reynolds number (Re) represents the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces in the flow, where: ρ is Air density and U_∞ is Free-stream velocity.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

The continuity equation ensures mass conservation, where ρ is the fluid density and \mathbf{u} is the velocity vector. For an incompressible flow with constant viscosity, the momentum equation is:

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} \right) = -\nabla P + \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{F} \quad (2)$$

where P is the pressure, μ is the dynamic viscosity and \mathbf{F} represents external forces such as gravity.

2.3 Boundary conditions and solution procedure

The simulations were based on the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations to model turbulent flow behaviour. The k-omega SST turbulence model was employed due to its accuracy in predicting boundary layer separation and pressure distribution. The continuity, momentum, and energy equations were solved using the finite volume method with second-order discretization schemes for improved numerical accuracy.

The working fluid, air, was simulated under Normal Temperature and Pressure (NTP) conditions with properties including a density of 1.204 kg/m³, specific heat capacity of 1006.43 J/(kg·K), thermal conductivity of 0.0242 W/(m·K), and viscosity of 1.81 × 10⁻⁵ kg/(m·s). The airfoil material, aluminum, was assigned a density of 2719 kg/m³, specific heat capacity of 871 J/(kg·K), and thermal conductivity of 202.4 W/(m·K). The inlet boundary conditions are established with free-stream velocities of 2 m/s, 5 m/s, and 8 m/s, corresponding to Reynolds numbers of 1.3x10⁵, 3.2x10⁵ and 5.4x10⁵, respectively. At the outlet, atmospheric pressure is applied, ensuring a realistic interaction with the surrounding environment. A no-slip condition was imposed on the airfoil surface to accurately capture boundary layer effects. The turbulence intensity was specified at 1% to align with typical experimental wind tunnel conditions. A pressure-based solver was employed, utilizing the SIMPLE (Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations) algorithm for pressure-velocity coupling. To enhance solution accuracy, second-order upwind discretization was applied to momentum, turbulence, and pressure equations. The convergence criteria were set to 1×10⁻⁵ for continuity and momentum residuals, ensuring numerical stability and solution reliability.

2.4 Meshing Strategy and Grid Independence Study

A structured, high-resolution quad-dominant mesh was created using ANSYS Meshing to precisely capture the boundary layer dynamics and wake region. To improve accuracy in resolving pressure and velocity gradients, mesh refinement was applied around the leading and trailing edges of the airfoil, ensuring a maximum skewness below 0.86. Structured Meshing around NACA0017 airfoil has been presented in figure 2. the mesh growth rate parameter was set to 1.2, maintaining a smooth transition between elements and ensuring numerical stability throughout the simulation. Additionally, the y^+ value was maintained below 5 to enhance the accuracy, providing a refined representation of flow characteristics.

Figure 2: Meshing around NACA0017 airfoil

A grid independence study was conducted by analyzing four different mesh densities 1×10^5 , 2×10^5 , 3×10^5 and 4×10^5 elements. The optimal mesh configuration was selected as 3×10^5 which was based on the convergence of lift and drag coefficients, ensuring reliable aerodynamic predictions. Mesh independence study for lift and drag coefficients has been presented in figure 3. The results obtained from the present simulation are thoroughly compared with existing literature, demonstrating a good agreement. The close correlation between the current findings and those reported in previous studies (Atkins 2015) validates the accuracy and reliability of the numerical approach employed.

Figure 3: Mesh independence Study

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section examines the effect of the $Re \in (1 \times 10^5, 6 \times 10^5)$ to analyze the influence of key parameters on the flow field. The results of this investigation are presented through drag and lift coefficients, velocity contours, and pressure coefficient distributions, providing a comprehensive understanding of the aerodynamic behavior of the airfoil under varying flow conditions.

The fluctuation of the drag (C_D) and lift (C_L) coefficients with respect to the Re for the NACA0017 airfoil is depicted in Figure 4. The drag coefficient on the left graph decreases as Re rises, suggesting that flow resistance around the airfoil decreases as Reynolds numbers rise. On the other hand, the graph on the right shows an upward trend in the lift coefficient as Re increases, indicating better aerodynamic performance brought about by increased lift generation. According to these findings, the airfoil becomes more aerodynamically efficient as its Reynolds number increases because it experiences less drag and more lift.

Figure 4: Drag and Lift coefficients at different $Re \in (1 \times 10^5, 6 \times 10^5)$ for NACA0017

Figure 5 presents the velocity contour around a NACA 0017 airfoil for different $Re \in (1 \times 10^5, 6 \times 10^5)$. As the Re increases, the flow characteristics around the airfoil change significantly. At $Re=1.3 \times 10^5$, the velocity variation is relatively moderate, with smooth flow around the airfoil. The velocity contour near the leading edge increases significantly, creating a stronger velocity gradient around the airfoil for $Re=3.2 \times 10^5$. The high-speed flow is more dominant, with an increased velocity at the trailing edge and wake region, indicating stronger aerodynamic effects at $Re=5.4 \times 10^5$. The results suggest that with increasing Re , the flow acceleration around the airfoil intensifies, leading to greater pressure differences and consequently impacting the lift and drag forces on the airfoil.

Figure 5: Velocity contour at different $Re \in (1 \times 10^5, 6 \times 10^5)$ for NACA0017

The pressure coefficient distribution around a NACA 0017 airfoil at different $Re \in (1 \times 10^5, 6 \times 10^5)$ is illustrated in figure 6. As the Re increases, the pressure distribution around the airfoil becomes more pronounced. The leading edge experiences a region of high pressure, while the suction effect on the upper surface intensifies with increasing velocity. The pressure coefficient decreases near the stagnation point as velocity increases, indicating stronger suction on the airfoil. Additionally, the wake region behind the airfoil also shows a variation in pressure distribution, which can impact drag characteristics. These changes suggest that increasing velocity influences both lift and drag forces, with potential implications for aerodynamic performance and flow separation behavior.

Figure 6: Pressure coefficient at different $Re \in (1 \times 10^5, 6 \times 10^5)$ for NACA0017

4. CONCLUSION

This study successfully analysed the aerodynamic performance of the NACA 0017 airfoil at a 0° angle of attack using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations for different $Re \in (1 \times 10^5, 6 \times 10^5)$. The use of CFD simulations in ANSYS Fluent allowed for a detailed examination of airflow behaviour around the airfoil, highlighting key aerodynamic characteristics such as pressure distribution, velocity profiles, and drag forces. By conducting the study under Normal Temperature and Pressure (NTP) conditions, the analysis ensured accurate representation of real-world scenarios where air properties remain consistent. Additionally, selecting aluminium as the airfoil material provided insights into its structural and thermal behaviour, which is essential in practical engineering applications. The results predicted that, as expected for a symmetric airfoil at a neutral orientation, minimal lift was generated, while the drag coefficient was well-characterized under subsonic flow conditions. The findings align closely with theoretical predictions and available experimental data, reinforcing the validity of the computational approach in aerodynamic analysis. The results are analyzed and presented

through key aerodynamic parameters, including the drag coefficient, lift coefficient, velocity contours, and pressure coefficient across various Reynolds numbers. These findings provide valuable insights into the influence of flow characteristics on airfoil performance, highlighting variations in aerodynamic forces and pressure distribution. The velocity contours illustrate flow separation and wake formation, while the pressure coefficient distribution helps in understanding the pressure gradient around the airfoil. By examining these parameters, the study offers a comprehensive assessment of the aerodynamic behavior of the NACA0017 airfoil under different flow conditions. This study serves as a fundamental step in understanding the aerodynamic behavior of symmetric airfoils, particularly in applications where minimal lift and balanced aerodynamic forces are required, such as in control surfaces, helicopter rotors, and wind turbine blades. The computational approach proved to be a reliable and efficient method for evaluating airfoil performance, reducing the need for extensive experimental testing while maintaining high accuracy. However, further investigations can be conducted to enhance the understanding of its aerodynamic behaviour and broaden its applicability.

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